

Structure, biomedical study and Hirshfeld surface analysis of sulfamethoxazolyl-azo-paracetamol and its copper(II) complex[†]

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[N-(4-Hydroxy-3-((4-(N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)sulfamoyl)phenyl)diazanyl)phenyl)acetamide] (HL, **1**) has been structurally established by the single crystal X-ray measurements along with other spectroscopic data. The packing shows H-bonded (both inter- and intra-molecular) 1D supramolecular chain through O(2)-H(2)---N(2)-C(5)-C(6)-O(2)-H(2)---N(2)-C(5)-C(6)-O(2) along the b axis generates a R₂²(12) cyclic motif of interlayer distance 3.57 Å. The intermolecular interactions in the crystal structure of ligand (HL) have been determined using Hirshfeld surfaces computational method and related quantitative information is conferred by fingerprint plots. The interaction of CT-DNA with [Cu(L)₂] (K_b^{Cu}, 1.69x10⁶ M⁻¹) complex is stronger than HL (K_b^{HL}, 1.9x10⁵ M⁻¹). Antimicrobial activities of these compounds have been measured against *B. subtilis* (ATCC 6633) and comparative data are IC₅₀: 163 µg/ml (HL) (**1**) and 114 µg/ml (**2**). Interaction with *E. coli* (ATCC 8739) shows IC₅₀ 241 µg/ml (HL) (**1**) and 134 µg/ml (**2**) somewhat higher data than *B. subtilis*.

Keywords: Sulfamethoxazole-azo-paracetamol, Hirshfeld surface analysis, Cu^{II} complex, biomedical study of sulfamethoxazolyl-azo-paracetamol.

Introduction

Paracetamol and sulfamethoxazole (Scheme 1) are both used in public life as common drugs. Paracetamol is a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory, non-narcotic analgesic and antipyretic agent that is widely used for the recovery of pain and fever^{1,2}. It has also antioxidant activity in many biological model of the lipid per oxidation³. Sulfamethoxazole (SMX)

is a member in sulfonamide family as prominent antibacterial drug and has revolutionized the history of antibiotics in medical science^{4,5}. Sulfonamides are structurally analogue to *p*-aminobenzoic acid (PABA) and acts as competitive inhibitor to dihydropterate synthetase, an enzyme that facilitates PABA as a substrate for the synthesis of dihydrofolic acid and perform as drug with a broad spectrum activity in

Scheme 1. Synthetic procedure of ligand (HL) followed by diazotization reaction.

[†]Invited Lecture.

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several infections².

In spite of their wide spread applications, overuse of paracetamol and SMX can lead to the accumulation of toxic metabolites that may induce painful side effects. For example, overdose of paracetamol causes fatal hepatotoxicity^{6–8}, asthma, eczema, allergic rhinitis^{9–12}. It affects development of fetus and central nervous system (CNS)^{13,14}. Similarly, excess use of sulfonamides may cause liver disease, kidney injury, skin rashes, drug fever, lung infection and hemolytic anemia⁵; disturb Ca^{2+} uptake in cells. Excess accumulation of paracetamol may inhibit or assist surplus secretion of different enzymes such as alanine *trans* aminase which is responsible for liver disfunction and hepatotoxicity^{6–8}. Similarly overconsumption of SMX results oxidative metabolites such as SMX-hydroxylamine (SMX-NHOH) and SMX-nitroso (SMX-NO)¹⁵ who are responsible for hypersensitivity.

In order to tackle these difficulties and to improve the efficiency, the drugs may be functionalized so that new molecules may coordinate to biological metal ions. Towards this target we have synthesized series of azo-sulfonamides (Ar-N=N-sulfonamide)¹⁶ and azomethine-sulfonamides (Ar-CH=N-sulfonamide)^{17,18}. Some of these new molecules have been used to synthesize metal complexes¹⁶. With this intention SMX is diazotized and coupled with phenol drug, paracetamol to synthesize N-(4-hydroxy-3-((4-(N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)sulfamoyl)phenyl)diazenyl)phenyl)acetamide (HL). Azo dyes of sulfa drugs are well known for their antiseptic activity^{15,19}. A large number of metal sulphonamide complexes are found to be more potent than the parent sulphonamides²⁰. Furthermore, azo compounds were reported to show a variety of biological activities including antibacterial^{21–23} and anti-inflammatory²⁴ activities. Azo compounds are known to be involved in a number of biological reactions such as inhibition of DNA, RNA, and protein synthesis, carcinogenesis, and nitrogen fixation²⁵. Azo dyes have been used in dyeing textile fibers, biomedical studies, advanced application in organic synthesis and high technology areas like lasers, liquid crystalline display, electro-optical devices and ink jet printer²⁶.

In this work, drug derivative HL carries N,O-chelating centres and has been used to synthesise Cu^{II} complex. The ligand and the complex have been characterized by spectroscopic data (FT-IR, UV-Vis, Mass, bulk magnetic moment,

EPR, EDX-SEM) and the structure of ligand has been confirmed by single crystal X-ray diffraction studies. The electronic properties have been computed from DFT and TD-DFT data of optimized geometry. The interaction of HL and their complex with CT-DNA are followed by spectroscopic experiments. Antimicrobial activities have also been examined with *E. coli* (Gram-negative) and *B. subtilis* (Gram-positive) bacteria.

Experimental

Materials:

Sulfamethoxazole (SMX) was acquired from Sigma-Aldrich Chemical Company and used without further purification. Paracetamol was purchased from Merck, India. The acetonitrile employed for electrochemical studies was dried with CaH_2 and distilled prior to use. The CT-DNA was purchased from Sisco Research Laboratories, India, and dissolved in phosphate buffer (pH ~7.4) containing 120 mM NaCl (AR grade, Merck, Germany). The purity of DNA was checked from the absorbance ratio A_{260}/A_{280} ²⁷. The concentration of CT-DNA in terms of nucleotide was determined by taking $\epsilon_{260} = 6600 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. NaCl (0.500 M dm^3) (AR grade, Merck, Germany) was used to maintain ionic strength.

Physical measurements:

The elemental analyses were executed on Perkin-Elmer model 2400 CHN/S elemental analyzers. Infrared spectra were carried out using Perkin-Elmer RX-1 FTIR spectrophotometer (KBr disk, 4000–400 cm^{-1}). The UV-Vis spectral data were achieved using Perkin-Elmer Lambda 25 UV-Visible spectrophotometer. ^1H NMR spectral data were collected in suitable solvent using AC Bruker 300, 500 MHz FT NMR spectrometers. The electrochemical studies were done with use of computer controlled CH Instruments Electrochemical Workstation. All experiments were done at 298 K under N_2 atmosphere with a three electrodes system, platinum and glassy carbon (GC) as working electrode in MeCN. All potentials are mentioned to the saturated calomel electrode (SCE) and are uncorrected for the junction contributions with n-tetra-butyl ammonium perchlorate, $[\text{nBu}_4\text{N}][\text{ClO}_4]$ (TBAP), as supporting electrolyte. The SEM-EDX analyses were carried out with the help of a computer controlled field emission SEM (JEOL, JSM-6330F, JEOL Ltd.) equipped with EDX detection system. Powder XRD analyses were carried out with the help of Machine Model – ULTIMA III Rigaku make

Japan Operating parameter – 40 Kv, 30 mA, Cu target, Ni filter and JCPDS Data Cards V.3.

Synthesis of *N*-(4-hydroxy-3-((4-(*N*-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)sulfamoyl)phenyl)diazenyl)phenyl)acetamide (HL) (1)

The diazotization of sulfamethoxazole (0.5 g, 1.97 mmol) (Scheme 1) was carried out at 0–5°C in aqueous solution by adding NaNO₂ (1.0 g) solution followed by coupling with paracetamol in presence of sodium carbonate (2.0 g) in water according to a general literature procedure¹⁸. Bright red-dish precipitate filtered and dried at room temperature. It was then recrystallized by slow evaporation of hot alcoholic solution and purity was examined by TLC; yield: 85%. Microanalytical data for HL (1): Anal. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₇N₅O₅S (Mol. wt. 415): C, 52.04; H, 4.12; N, 16.86%. Found (%): C, 51.95; H, 4.1; N, 16.76; FT-IR bands (KBr pellet, ν, cm⁻¹) ν(N=N), 1420.47; ν(C=N), 1616.74; ν(C=O), 1653.46; ν(O-H), 3364.02; ν(S-O), 1173.69. [M⁺] *m/z* 438. ¹H NMR data (DMSO-*d*₆, ppm): 6.188 (4H, s), 9.960 (19N-H, s), 8.141 (8,12H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz), 8.029 (9,11H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz), 7.038 (15H, d, *J* 8.7 Hz), 7.605 (16H, d, *J* 7.2 Hz), 10.590 (5N-H, s), 11.627 (14O-H, s), 2.302 (20 -CH₃, s), 2.02 (21 -CH₃, s).

Synthesis of [Cu(L)₂] (2) complex

To methanol solution (10 ml) of Cu(OAc)₂·H₂O: 30 mg, 0.150 mmol) in a round bottom flask two equivalent of HL (100 mg, 0.273 mmol) in MeOH (10 ml) and 0.1 ml of Et₃N were added and stirred (Scheme 2). The solution was stirred for 4 h followed by 6 h refluxing and then cooled to room temperature, settled and filtered. Residue was washed with MeOH-water (1:1, v/v), ash colored copper complex was recrystallized from DMF-methanol (1:4, v/v) mixture.

Microanalytical data for [Cu(L)₂] (2): Anal. Calcd. for CuC₃₆H₃₂N₁₀O₁₀S₂ (Mol. wt. 892): C, 48.45; H, 3.61; N, 15.70; S, 7.19%. Found (%): C, 48.10; H, 3.54; N, 15.05; S, 7.03. [M⁺] *m/z* 900 FT-IR (KBr, ν, cm⁻¹) ν(N=N), 1419.68; ν(C=N), 1612.98; ν(C=O), 1656.64; ν(O-H), 3451.22; ν(S-O), 1142.78. Spectra of both ligand and complex are given in Supplementary Materials (Figs. S1-S5).

X-Ray crystal structure analysis of HL (1):

HL was crystallized by slow diffusion of mixture of dichloromethane with hexane solution (1:1, v/v). The relevant crystal structure data along with structure determination details are listed in Table 1. Data were collected by Bruker Smart Apex II CCD Area Detector at 293(2) K. Diffraction was re-

Scheme 2. Synthetic procedure for [Cu(L)₂] (2) complex.

corded with θ in the range $2.12 \leq \theta \leq 25.00^\circ$ (HL). Fine-focus sealed tube was used as the radiation source of graphite-monochromatized MoK α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$). Data were corrected for Lorentz and polarization effects and an empirical absorption correction in the *h k l* range for $-9 \leq h \leq 9$; $-11 \leq k \leq 11$; $-15 \leq l \leq 15$ for HL. Multi-scan absorption corrections were applied²⁸. The structure was solved by direct methods with SHELX-97²⁹ and refined by full-matrix least-squares techniques on *F*² using the SHELX-97³⁰ program with anisotropic displacement parameters for all non-hydrogen atoms. Programs SHELXL-97 and ORTEP-3³¹ were used within WinGX³² to prepare materials for publication. Hydrogen atoms were constrained to ride on the respective carbon atoms with isotropic displacement parameters equal to 1.2 times the equivalent to displacement of their parent atom in all cases of aromatic units.

Hirshfeld surface analysis:

Hirshfeld surfaces^{33,34} and associated 2D-fingerprint³⁵ plots were analyzed using CrystalExplorer 3.1³⁶ that receives structure input file in CIF format. For each point on the Hirshfeld isosurface, two distances d_e , the distance from the point to the nearest nucleus outside to the surface, and d_i , the distance to the nearest nucleus inside to the surface. The normalized contact distance (d_{norm}) has been defined in terms of d_e , d_i and the van der Waals (vdw) radii of the atoms

Table 1. Crystal data and structure refinement for HL (1)

Empirical formula	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₅ S	
Formula weight	415.44	
Temperature	296(2) K	
Wavelength	0.71073 Å	
Crystal system	Triclinic	
Space group	P-1	
Unit cell dimensions	$a = 7.7047(6)$ Å	$\alpha = 95.130(4)^\circ$
	$b = 10.2713(9)$ Å	$\beta = 92.968(4)^\circ$
	$c = 12.8465(11)$ Å	$\gamma = 109.511(4)^\circ$
Volume	950.80(14) Å ³	
Z	2	
Density (calculated)	1.451 mg/m ³	
Absorption coefficient	0.212 mm ⁻¹	
F (000)	432	
Crystal size	0.32×0.28×0.26 mm ³	
Theta range for data collection	2.12 to 25.00°	
Index ranges	-9,9; -11,12; -15,15	
Reflections collected	15275	
Independent reflections	3347	
Max. and min. transmission	0.934 and 0.946	
Refinement method	Full-matrix least-squares on F ²	
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	1.139	
Final R indices [I > 2 sigma (I)] ^a	R1 = 0.0432, wR2 = 0.1407	
R indices (all data) ^b	R1 = 0.0373, wR2 = 0.1318	
^a R = $\sum F_o - F_c / \sum F_o$. ^b wR = $[\sum w(F_o^2 - F_c^2) / \sum w F_o^4]^{1/2}$ are general but w are different, $w = 1 / [\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (0.1000P)^2 + 0.0000P]$ for HL.		

is given by the eq. (1)³⁷.

$$d_{\text{norm}} = \frac{d_i - r_i^{\text{vdw}}}{r_i^{\text{vdw}}} + \frac{d_e - r_e^{\text{vdw}}}{r_e^{\text{vdw}}} \quad (1)$$

where r_i^{vdw} and r_e^{vdw} are the van der Waals radii of atoms. d_{norm} has been visualized using a red-white-blue color scheme whereas red emphasizes shorter contact, white zone depicts contacts around the vdw separation and blue is for longer contacts. In addition, two further colored properties based on the local curvature of the surface can be precised³⁸ e.g. shape index and curvedness.

Antibacterial studies of HL (1) and [Cu(L)₂] (2) complex:

The antibacterial activity of HL and the complex [Cu(L)₂] (2) had been executed to get their efficiency towards bacteria. The compounds had been dissolved in 100% DMSO and stored at -20°C. Gram-positive *B. subtilis* (ATCC 6633)

and Gram-negative *E. coli* (ATCC 8739), inoculated in a freshly prepared autoclaved LB broth from a 24 h old LA slant, and were kept in shaker for overnight. Then it was diluted with sterile LB to a final bacterial count of 1×10⁴ cfu/ml. The diluted culture was distributed in a number of tubes and incubated in the absence as well as in the presence of various concentrations of test compounds. All the tubes were incubated for 16–18 h at 37°C in shaking condition and the OD₆₀₀ had been calculated in a UV-Visible spectrophotometer. The OD₆₀₀ value observed in the growth control (without any drug) had been considered as control with 100% growth for both the bacterial species. Compared to control the relative degree of bacterial growth inhibition had been calculated for each set of ligand concentrations incubated under similar experimental condition from a measurement of OD at 600 nm. The minimum inhibitory concentrations (IC₅₀) i.e. the concentration of test compound required to inhibit the growth of bacteria by 50% had been calculated from the % reduction of bacterial growth in comparison to control.

Interaction of HL and [Cu(L)₂] complex with calf thymus DNA:

Preparation of solutions for DNA binding studies:

A stock solution (10 ml) of HL (1) and [Cu(L)₂] (2) complex were made by dissolving (1.3 mg, 0.313 mmol of 1 and 1.3 mg, 0.134 mmol of 2) in DMSO. These solutions were diluted with tris-HCl buffer for preparation of working cell concentration for the experiment. Absorption spectral titration experiment was done by keeping constant concentration of the complex with varying concentration of CT-DNA. To eliminate the absorbance of DNA itself, equal solution of CT-DNA was added either to HL or [Cu(L)₂] solution.

Preparation of calf thymus DNA:

The tris-HCl buffer solution (pH 8.0), involving CT-DNA, was prepared by using de-ionized and sonicated HPLC grade water (Merck). The CT-DNA used in the experiments was sufficiently free from protein. The concentration of DNA was measured by the dint of its extinction coefficient ϵ of 6600 mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 260 nm¹⁷. Stock solution of DNA was always kept at 4°C and used within 4 days.

Absorption spectroscopic studies of the complexes in presence of CT DNA:

Absorption spectroscopic studies were carried out on a spectrophotometer (Perkin-Elmer, Lambda-25), using HL (1)

and $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2]$ (**2**) complex with increasing concentrations of CT-DNA (0, 0.502, 1.0, 1.49, 1.98, 2.46, 2.94, 3.415 μM) and (0, 0.502, 1.0, 1.49, 1.98 μM). After each addition, the mixture of DNA and the compounds were incubated at room temperature for 15 min and scanned at 250–600 nm wave length for the above compounds. The self-absorption of DNA was eliminated in each set of experiments. Each sample was scanned for a cycle number of 2, cycle time of 5 s at a scan speed of 100 nm/min. Modified Benesi-Hildebrand¹⁶ plot was used for the determination of ground state binding constant between the compounds and CT-DNA. The binding constant K_b was determined by using the relation $A_0/\Delta A = A_0/\Delta A_{\text{max}} + (A_0/\Delta A_{\text{max}}) \times (1/K) \times (1/L_t)$ where $\Delta A = A_0 - A$, ΔA_{max} = maximum change in reduced absorbance, A_0 = maximum absorbance of receptor molecules (without any DNA), A = reduced absorbance of receptor molecules (in presence of DNA), L_t = DNA concentration.

Computational aspects:

HL (**1**) and $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2]$ (**2**) compounds were used as input functions in the Density functional theory (DFT) calculations and the optimized geometries of **1** and **2** were generated. The calculations have been carried out with the B3LYP-6-31G(d) basis set for C, H, N, Cl and LanL2DZ³⁹ is used for Cu and S using the Gaussian 09 program. The entire calculations including graphical representations of the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) data in the checkpoint files were carried out⁴⁰ with the aid of the Gauss View visualization program^{41,42}. The vibrational frequency calculations were performed to ensure that the optimized geometries represent the local minima and there are only positive eigen val-

ues. Vertical electronic excitations based on B3LYP optimized geometries was computed for HL and the complexes using the time-dependent density functional theory (TD-DFT) formalism^{43–45} in dichloromethane using conductor-like polarizable continuum model (CPCM)^{46–48}. Gauss Sum was used to calculate the fractional contributions of various groups to each molecular orbital⁴¹.

Results and discussion

The synthesis and formulation:

4-((7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-2-oxo-3,8a-dihydro-2H-chromen-6-yl)diazenyl)-N-(5-methylisoxazole-3-yl)benzenesulfonamide (HL) (**1**) (Scheme 1) has been synthesized following published procedure¹⁷ by diazotization of sulfamethoxazole (SMX) followed by the coupling of diazonium ion (SMX-N=N^+) with paracetamol in basic medium yielded reddish crystal of (HL) (**1**) [SMX-N=N-PARA]. The further reaction among the ligand (HL) (**1**) and $[\text{Cu}(\text{OAc})_2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ yielded light green crystals of $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2]$ (**2**) complex (Scheme 2). The ligand (HL) (**1**) and $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2]$ (**2**) complex have been isolated and characterized by spectroscopic data (FT-IR, ¹H NMR and Mass (Supplementary Materials, Figs. S1-S5).

The X-ray powder diffraction pattern of $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2]$ (**2**) has been taken to define the crystallinity of the molecules (Supplementary Material, Figs. S6). Diffraction pattern and SEM image shows that the complex **2** is amorphous (Fig. 1 a,b). The chemical analyses by EDX for the complex show a homogeneous distribution between metal ions and chelating agent which determines the elemental composition. The analyses of $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2]$ reveals that O, C and N appear at K_{α} peak 0.51 KeV, 0.10 KeV and 0.20 KeV respectively, but sulphur shows

Fig. 1. Elemental EDX microanalyses spectrum of $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2]$ (**2**) (a) complex. The peaks are labeled with the EDX lines of the corresponding element. Different morphology images of $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2]$ (**2**) (b) complex through SEM study.

K_{α} peak at 2.3 KeV⁴⁹ along with Cu K_{α} peak at 8 KeV, 8.9 KeV and 1 KeV (Supplementary Materials, Table S1).

The magnetic moment is recorded at 305 K and μ_{eff} is 1.57 BM for **(2)**. These data support d^9 electronic configuration of $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2]$ (**2**) of the complex. The EPR spectra at solid state shows existence of active paramagnetic electron to Cu^{II} in Fig. 2. The complex shows usual four line (^{63}Cu , $I = 3/2$) EPR spectra and are anisotropic at higher magnetic field. They exhibit axial spectra with $g_{\parallel} 2.24$. The results are in general agreement with the electronic spectra, which also suggest the existence of octahedral. From the observed g -tensor values of the Cu^{II} complexes it is clear that $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp}$ agrees with the ground state configuration of $d_{x^2-y^2}$ giving $^2B_{1g}$ as the ground state. The cyclic voltammogram of HL and $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2]$ (**2**) complex in acetonitrile show irreversible azo reduction at -1.0 V (ΔE , 200 mV) (Supplementary Materials, Fig. S7 a,b).

Fig. 2. EPR spectra of $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2]$ (**2**) at room temperature.

Absorption spectrum of HL in MeOH shows intense absorption at 326 (ϵ , 4×10^4) and 425 nm (ϵ , 1.3×10^4); $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2]$ (**2**) absorbs in DMF at 326 (ϵ , 9×10^4) and 487 nm (ϵ , 4.1×10^4) given in Supplementary Materials, Table S2. The d-d band in DMF solution of the complex appears at 536 nm (**2**) and absorption spectrum are given in Supplementary Materials, Fig. S8 a,b. The spectral features are routine; however DFT and TD-DFT computation have been attempted using optimised geometries of the molecules to explain the electronic transitions. To simplify analysis of DFT computation result the structure of HL has been divided (Scheme 3 under Fig. 3) into benzene sulfonamide (SLMD), methyloxazolyl (MOX) and azo-paracetamol (APA). The composition of MOs and proposed electronic transitions in acetonitrile (CH_3CN) solution of HL (**1**) and $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2]$ (**2**) suggest that azo function

(APA) is electron acceptor while methyloxazolyl (MOX) and benzene sulfonamide (SLMD) either separately or jointly donate electrons. The composition of MOs of HL and proposed electronic transitions in acetonitrile (CH_3CN) solution shown in Supplementary Materials, Table S3 suggest that azo function (APA) is electron acceptor while methyloxazolyl (MOX) and benzene sulfonamide (SLMD) either separately or jointly donate electrons; HOMO \rightarrow LUMO+1 refers to SLMD \rightarrow APA (359.27 nm, f , 0.6689); HOMO-2 \rightarrow LUMO refers to MOX \rightarrow APA and BSLMD \rightarrow APA (353.15 nm; f , 0.0636). In HL, the electronic transitions at 425 nm is due to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition. For complex **2**, the composition of MOs and proposed electronic transitions in acetonitrile (CH_3CN) solution shown in Supplementary Materials, Tables S4-S6. Contour plots of HOMO and LUMO of complex **2** and spin density are shown in Fig. 3. Molecular orbital of ligand is shown in Supplementary Material, Fig. S9.

In case of molecular orbital of $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2]$, the HOMO is constituted of 5% SLMD, 2% MOX, 93% APA; the LUMO has 19% contribution from SLMD, 80% APA and 1% from MOX (Supplementary Material, Fig. S10). So, the HOMO \rightarrow LUMO may be assigned to intra-molecular charge transfer from APA \rightarrow APA. In $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2]$, the electronic transitions at 487 nm is due to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition. In CH_3CN the calculated transition appears at 484.30 nm (f , 0.0208) for molecular orbital of $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2]$. The observed transitions are close to the calculated molecular orbital of $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2]$.

Crystal structure description of HL (**1**):

Molecular structure of HL (**1**) with atom numbering scheme is shown in Fig. 4 and selected bond parameters are listed in Table 1. The theoretical bond length and bond angle of HL (**1**) generated from DFT optimization technique and experimental bond distances and angles are summarized in Table 2. Two aromatic groups, benzene ring of paracetamol and methyl-oxazolyl, are bonded to $-\text{SO}_2\text{NH}-$ (sulfonamide) function. The S=O bond length 1.421(3), 1.430(3) Å is corroborated with literature data. The N(3)-N(2) bond lengths in HL is 1.2610(19) Å, which matched well with N=N bond lengths reported¹⁶. The crystal packing shows H-bonded (both inter- and intra-molecular) 1D supramolecular chain through O(2)-H(2) \cdots N(2)-C(5)-C(6)-O(2)-H(2) \cdots N(2)-C(5)-C(6)-O(2) along the b axis generates a $R_2^2(12)$ cyclic motif of inter layer distance 3.57 Å and shows intra-molecular H-bonding (Fig. 5). Inter-hydrogen bonding interactions occurs N(2)-H(2)-O(2)

Fig. 3. Contour plots of HOMO and LUMO of HL (1) and [Cu(L)₂(H₂O)₄] (2) compounds.

whose distance is 2.50 Å. An interesting interaction among nitrogen lone pair of azo moiety with π of paracetamol benzene ring is shown in Fig. 6. One dimensional assembly of

monomeric units of HL through interaction of lone pair of O of SO₂--- π of oxazolyl ring and π --- π interaction occurs between two sulfonamide benzene ring shown in Figs. 7-8. The

Fig. 4. Representation of single crystal X-ray structure of HL (**1**), showing labeling.

DFT optimized structure of HL, we may conclude that the theoretically generated parameters of the ligand may closer to would be structure of the complex. Thus molecular functions generated from the proposed structures may be acceptable for explaining experimental results and reported result⁴⁹. The structures are also generated by DFT computation and the agreement has been verified on comparing the bond distances and angles between the DFT optimized and X-ray determined structure of HL. It is observed than bond distances are varying within 0.05–0.1 Å and the bond angles vary 1–5° (Table 2).

Table 2. Theoretical and experimental bond length (Å) and bond angle (°) of HL (**1**)

Bond distance between two atoms	Experimental value (Å)	Theoretical value (Å)	Bond angle among the atoms	Experimental value (°)	Theoretical value (°)
S(1)-O(4)	1.4240(13)	1.6304	N(2)-N(3)-C(9)	114.50(14)	116.03
S(1)-O(3)	1.4225(13)	1.6302	N(3)-N(2)-C(5)	116.01(14)	117.05
S(1)-C(12)	1.7624(18)	1.8752	C(2)-N(1)-C(3)	128.03(15)	127.99
S(1)-N(4)	1.6176(16)	1.8286	O(2)-C(6)-C(5)	122.44(17)	121.81
C(9)-N(3)	1.422(2)	1.4195	O(1)-C(2)-N(1)	122.87(17)	123.33
N(3)-N(2)	1.2610(19)	1.2934	N(2)-C(5)-C(6)	124.85(16)	123.92
C(5)-N(2)	1.399(2)	1.3953	C(14)-C(9)-N(3)	116.34(16)	116.10
C(3)-N(1)	1.408(2)	1.4116	O(4)-S(1)-N(4)	107.78(8)	106.80
C(2)-O(1)	1.227(2)	1.2492	O(4)-S(1)-O(3)	120.73(9)	123.34
C(2)-N(1)	1.353(2)	1.3814			

Fig. 5. Formation of 1D tape in HL through association of discrete HL monomeric units. The occurrence of inter hydrogen bonding interactions O(2)-(H2).....N(2) along the b axis generates a R₂²(12) cyclic motif.

Fig. 6. Formation of 1D tape in HL through association of discrete HL monomeric units. The occurrence of inter hydrogen bonding interactions N(2)---H(2)-O(2) along the b axis.

bond angle \angle O(4)-S(1)-O(3) is 120.73. The structures of the complexes **2** and **3** (Scheme 2) have been generated from DFT optimization technique and the bond distances and angles are summarized in Table 3. Relevant H bonds are given in Table 4. On comparing with the X-ray structure and

Hirshfeld surface analysis:

The Hirshfeld surfaces of ligand (HL) are illustrated in Fig. 9 shown surfaces that have been mapped over d_e range 0.716 to 2.663 Å, a d_f range 0.717 to 2.637 Å, a d_{norm} range of -0.644 to 1.376 Å, a shape index of -0.991 to 0.998 Å and

Fig. 7. Three dimensional assembly of monomeric units of HL having C-H... π and π ...C-H interaction of benzene ring and lone pair of azo N... π and π ...C-H interaction. The extended network is shown in green dotted lines. This assembly is viewed along the b axis.

Fig. 8. One dimensional assembly of monomeric units of HL through interaction of lone pair of O of SO₂... π of oxazole ring and π ... π interaction occurs between two sulfonamide benzene.

Table 3. Theoretical bond length (Å) and bond angle (°) of [Cu(L)₂] (2)

Length type	Theoretical	[Cu(L) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	
		Bond length (Å)	Bond angle (°)
N(10)-N(11)	1.276	N(44)-N(34)-C(35)	124.85
N(34)-N(44)	1.280	N(10)-N(11)-C(12)	114.01
Cu(91)-N(11)	2.057	N(34)-N(44)-C(45)	112.07
Cu(91)-O(89)	1.910	N(10)-N(11)-C(01)	122.30
Cu(91)-O(88)	1.930	O(83)-S(22)-O(82)	123.21
N(11)-C(12)	1.425	O(85)-S(55)-O(84)	120.77
N(34)-C(35)	1.360	O(82)-S(22)-N(23)	103.50
S(22)-O(82)	1.459	O(85)-S(55)-N(56)	105.71
		O(82)-S(22)-C(10)	108.35

curvedness of -3.741 to 0.202 Å respectively. The fingerprint plots which summarize the intermolecular interaction in the crystal structure are depicted in Fig. 10 and suggest the possibility of getting both qualitative and quantitative insights into

Table 4. Hydrogen bonding interactions for HL

D-H...A	D-H	H...A	D...A	\angle D-H...A
N(1)-H(1)...N(5)i	0.86	2.40	3.153(3)	147
O(2)-H(2)...N(2)	0.82	2.51	2.928(2)	113
O(2)-H(2)...N(3)	0.82	1.88	2.571(2)	141
N(4)-H(4A)...O(1)iii	0.86	1.94	2.785(2)	168
C(4)-H(4)...O(1)iv	0.93	2.37	2.898(2)	115
C(11)-H(11)...O(3)v	0.93	2.47	2.865(3)	105
C(13)-H(13)...O(4)iii	0.93	2.59	3.497(2)	165
C(14)-H(14)...O(3)	0.93	2.55	3.378(3)	149
C(16)-H(16)...O(3)	0.93	2.49	3.352(3)	154

Symmetry: ⁱ-x,-y,-z, ⁱⁱ1-x,-y,-z, ⁱⁱⁱ1-x,1-y,1-z, ^{iv}-1+x,y,z, ^v2-x,1-y,1-z

Fig. 9.

the intermolecular interaction of the crystal. The surfaces are shown as transparent to allow visualization structure moiety. The d_{norm} surface presents the contacts of hydrogen bond donors and acceptors but other close contact are also evident. In d_{norm} surfaces the large circular depression (deep red) indicates the H-bonding contacts whereas other visible spots are owing to H...H contacts. The leading H...O interaction in the title crystal structure are viewed in the Hirshfeld surface plots by the bright red area (Fig. 11) and light red spots are due to C-H...O interaction. The π ... π stacking was observed in d_{norm} and curvedness surfaces (Fig. 11) that are used to determine the way in which the molecules overlap and make contact with each other. The small extent of area and light color on the surface expresses weaker and longer contacts other than H bond. The relative contribution of the different interactions to the Hirshfeld surfaces were determined for ligand (HL) (Fig. 12).

Fig. 10. Fingerprint plots: full (upper left) and resolved into different intermolecular interactions with the title ligand (HL) showing percentage of contacts contributing to the total Hirshfeld surface area of the molecules.

Antibacterial potential of HL and $[Cu(L)_2]$:

Antimicrobial activity of HL (**1**) and $[Cu(L)_2]$ (**2**) complex have been examined against *B. subtilis* (ATCC 6633) and *E. coli* (ATCC 8739). They exhibit inhibition of bacterial growth after 18–20 h of compound administration. The IC_{50} (the concentration of test compound required to inhibit the growth of bacteria by 50%) of the compounds have been compared with the precursor drug, SMX and presented in Fig. 13a,b. There is a gradual diminish of bacterial growth evident from the diagram with the increase of compound concentration for both the Gram-positive as well as Gram-negative bacteria. The IC_{50} values of the various derivatives of SMX against Gram-negative *E. coli* (ATCC 8739) are 241 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (**1**), 134 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (**2**) compared to the value of 300 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ estimated for SMX. The same trend has also been maintained against Gram-positive *B. subtilis* (ATCC 6633) with the IC_{50} values 163 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (**1**), 114 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (**2**) and 176 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (SMX) respec-

tively. This manifests the relative increased potency of the present compounds (**1-2**) over the precursor drug, SMX. The antibacterial effect of metal ions has been utilized since ancient past and the term “oligodynamic action” has been envisaged to demonstrate this antibacterial role of the metal ions. Nowadays there is a resurgence of interest to combat bacterial resistance against commonly used drugs like SMX⁵⁰. Sulfonamide resistance has been originated from the single amino acid mutations in the chromosomal *dhps* gene of *E. coli* transmitted by the two drug-resistant dihydropteroate synthetase (DHPS) enzymes, encoded by *sull* or *sullI* genes⁵⁰. Occurrence of *sull* and *sullI* has been noticed among sulfonamide-resistant Gram-negative enteric bacteria with almost equal frequency. Apart from that role of the drug efflux pumps, has been implicated for mediating resistance to SMX^{51,52}.

Fig. 11. Hirshfeld surfaces mapped with d_{norm} (a), shape index (b) and curvedness (c) for ligand (HL) showing different type supramolecular interactions.

Fig. 12. Relative contribution of different intermolecular contacts to the Hirshfeld surface area of ligand (HL).

Interaction of the complexes with CT-DNA: Absorption spectroscopic studies:

The interaction of HL (**1**) and $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2]$ (**2**) with CT-DNA have been investigated by spectrophotometric method. Ad-

Fig. 13. The minimum inhibitory concentrations (IC_{50}) of HL (**1**), $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2]$ (**2**) and SMX in the presence of *B. subtilis* (ATCC 6633) (a) and *E. coli* (ATCC 8739) (b).

dition of increasing amounts of CT-DNA resulted in an increase in absorbency without any shift in the absorption maxima (425 nm for **1** and 487 nm for **2** complex) in the UV spectra. In general, an intercalative interaction of the aromatic chromophore and the base pairs of DNA helix are reflected by hyperchromism and red shift of charge transfer band. The spectral changes of HL (**1**) and $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2]$ (**2**) compounds observed in the presence of CT-DNA which can be illustrated in terms of groove binding⁵³ and Benesi-Hildebrand (BH) plot are shown in Figs. 14a,b; 15a,b. It is reported that aromatic ring of the molecule closely matches with the helical turn of the CT-DNA groove and interacts with DNA in Tris-HCl buffer through the formation of the van der Waal's contacts or hydrogen bonds in DNA grooves. At the absorption maximum, the binding constant (K_b) for HL (**1**) and $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2]$ (**2**) are $1.9 \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1}$ and $1.69 \times 10^6 \text{ M}^{-1}$ respectively with DNA by using modified Benesi-Hildebrand (BH) plot. The free energy ΔG^\ddagger are -7.24 kcal for HL (**1**) and -8.54 kcal for $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2]$ (**2**), respectively. A negative value of free energy is indicative of the spontaneity of the complex-DNA binding and implies better interaction with metal complexes compared to free ligand. The results support the interaction of the complexes with DNA through groove binding of the aromatic chromospheres and the base pairs of DNA. So complex **2** has better interaction with DNA than **1**. It is clear that IC_{50} value of both ligand and metal complex are less than the parent SMX molecule, so synthesized molecule are more biologically active than SMX but IC_{50} value of $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})_2]$ (**2**) is more than HL (**1**). In terms of DNA interaction it also proves that K_b value ($K_b^{\text{Cu}}, 1.69 \times 10^6 \text{ M}^{-1}$) is stronger than HL that shows least interaction ($K_b^{\text{HL}}, 1.9 \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1}$).

Fig. 14. (a) Presents absorption spectroscopic study of 0.313 mmol of HL (1) with increasing concentrations of CT-DNA (0, 0.502, 1, 1.49, 1.98, 2.46, 2.94, 3.4 μ M) respectively (1 \rightarrow 8) and (b) represents modified Benesi-Hildebrand plot for the determination of ground state binding constant between CT DNA with HL (1).

Fig. 15. (a) Presents absorption spectroscopic study of 0.0134 mmol of $[Cu(L)_2]$ (2) with increasing concentrations of CT-DNA (0, 0.502, 1, 1.49, 1.98 μ M) respectively (1 \rightarrow 5) and (b) represents modified Benesi-Hildebrand plot for the determination of ground state binding constant between CT-DNA with $[Cu(L)_2]$ (2).

Conclusion

N-(4-Hydroxy-3-((4-(N-(5-methylisoxazol-3-yl)sulfamoyl)phenyl)diazenyl)phenyl)acetamide (HL) (1), a derivative of two drugs paracetamol and sulfamethoxazole, has been used to synthesize Cu^{II} complex, $[Cu(L)_2]$ (2) and have been characterized by IR, Mass, EPR, EDX-SEM and X-Ray. Interaction of HL and $[Cu(L)_2]$ (2) with CT-DNA has been followed by absorption spectroscopic study and the antibacterial activity is examined against *B. subtilis* (ATCC 6633) and *E. coli*

(ATCC 8739). Free ligand, HL shows better efficiency to antimicrobial activity against *E. coli* and *B. subtilis* than its complex and also better than common drug, SMX.

Abbreviations

SMX: Sulfamethoxazole, CT-DNA: Calf thymus DNA, MIC: Minimum inhibitory concentration, Ligand (HL): Sulfamethoxazole-azo-acetylacetone, EDX: Energy dispersive X-ray spectrum.

Supporting Information

Crystallographic data for the structure have been deposited to the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center, CCDC No. 982338 for compound HL. These data can be obtained free of charge via <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/conts/retrieving.html>, or from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK; Fax: (+44) 1223-336-033; or E-mail: deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk.

Supplementary materials

Physicochemical data of the compounds are given in as follows: FT-IR, Figs. S1-S2, NMR spectra, Fig. S3; Mass, Figs. S4-S5; Powder-XRD, Fig. S6; Cyclic voltammogram, Fig. S7 a,b; UV-Vis and d-d band, Fig. S8 a,b; FMOs of HL, Fig. S9, FMOs of [Cu(L)₂], Fig. S10; Elemental EDX microanalysis of [Cu(L)₂] (2), Table S1; UV-Vis of compounds, Table S2; Composition and energy of the molecular levels and TDFT of compounds, Tables S3-S6.

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